

PERCEPTIONS AND PREPAREDNESS OF COMPUTER SCIENCE EDUCATION LECTURERS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN TEACHING IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

This study examined the perceptions and preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions, and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population comprised all 1,233 Computer Science Education (CSE) lecturers in Nigeria (Universities: 684, Colleges of Education: 398 and Polytechnics: 151). A purposive sampling technique was used to select 123 respondents as the sample size (71 male and 52 female CSE lecturers). Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Perceptions and Preparedness of Computer Science Education Lecturers for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Integration in Teaching Questionnaire (PPCSELAITQ). The instrument was validated by three research experts and Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability which yielded 0.83 as an overall reliability index. Mean, standard deviation, and independent sample t-test were used to answer the research questions as well as testing of the null hypotheses. Findings indicated that CSE lecturers generally held positive perceptions of AI integration, but their preparedness for implementing AI in teaching was moderate. The study conclude that lecturers are aware of the advantages that AI can bring to teaching, but many still lack the skills and resources to use it effectively. In line with the findings, the study recommended among others that tertiary institutions should provide targeted training programme to equip CSE lecturers with the practical skills needed for AI-based teaching.

Keywords: Computer Science Education, Artificial Intelligence Integration, Lecturers' Perceptions, Teaching Preparedness, Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

Introduction

Computer science education is the teaching and learning of the principles and applications of computer science, including algorithms, software and hardware design, programming, data, and the impact of computing on society. It goes beyond basic computer literacy by helping students understand how technology works, create new technologies, and develop critical computational thinking skills (Mouza, Yang, Pan, Ozden & Pollock, 2022). Computer science education includes various components such as coding, digital citizenship, educational technology, and information technology, aiming to prepare students for technology-driven careers and informed participation in a digital world. This field integrates educational methods and computer

science knowledge to effectively teach these concepts in schools and higher education through the use of Artificial Intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the latest form of computing technology, where systems are programmed to perform reasoning and problem-solving tasks typically carried out by humans (Aldosari, 2020). It enables machines to imitate human intelligence by allowing computers to think, understand, and solve problems intelligently (Buabbas, Al-Sharhan, Almajran & Buabbas, 2023). Lin (2022) explains that AI tools, as part of educational technology, are now widely applied in teaching and learning to enhance instructional delivery and improve learning outcomes. In Nigeria, the rise of AI in higher institutions is creating new opportunities to transform teaching,

learning, and school management (Ofem & Chukwujama, 2024). AI systems are designed to perform human-like tasks such as visual recognition, speech understanding, decision-making, and language translation (Ukala, Ukala & Chukwuemeka, 2025).

Lecturers' perception refers to how lecturers view, interpret, and understand a particular educational innovation, policy, or teaching approach based on their experiences and beliefs. It influences their willingness to adopt new methods and technologies in teaching and learning. According to Adeoye and Adeoye (2022), lecturers' perception determines the success or failure of educational innovations, as positive attitudes often lead to better implementation outcomes. Several studies have examined lecturers' perceptions and preparedness toward Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration in higher education. Mutanga, Jugoo, and Adefemi (2024) discovered that lecturers expressed mixed perceptions regarding the adoption of AI tools such as ChatGPT; while some actively used them to improve teaching and assessments, others resisted due to uncertainty and fears about their implications for teaching practices. Similarly, Sheu (2025) reported that lecturers in public tertiary institutions in Zamfara State recognized AI's potential to improve research quality and assessment validity, yet its practical use in research activities remained low.

In another study, Ezekiel and Akinyemi (2022) found that lecturers at the University of Ibadan generally viewed AI positively but were cautious about full adoption because of limited institutional readiness and ethical concerns. Likewise, Olorkor and Gideon (2024) observed that Agricultural Education lecturers in Southeast Nigerian universities appreciated AI's benefits for personalized learning and program efficiency but identified challenges such as poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, and lack of training. Supporting these findings, Mayor and Bautista (2025) revealed that faculty in higher institutions showed positive attitudes and strong preparedness toward AI integration, noting that favorable

perception and adaptability significantly influenced readiness levels. Lecturers' perception of Artificial Intelligence influences their willingness, confidence, and readiness to adopt it in teaching, reflecting their level of preparedness. Lecturers' preparedness describes the extent to which lecturers possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and resources to effectively carry out a specific teaching task or integrate new technologies into instruction. It involves their readiness through training, competence, and confidence to adapt to modern educational demands. Mmaduka, Albert, Ukala, and Ekpo (2025) observed that lecturers in Nigerian universities show moderate preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching due to limited infrastructure and inadequate training. A study conducted by Mmaduka, Albert, Ukala and Ekpo (2025) revealed that Nigerian universities, particularly the National Institute for Nigerian Languages, Aba, are only moderately prepared for the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching, due to limited infrastructure, inadequate staff training, and low awareness of AI applications in education. A slight disparity existed in lecturers' perception and preparedness for AI integration in teaching, with males showing higher readiness than females based on gender.

Gender refers to the social and cultural roles, behaviours, and expectations that societies assign to individuals based on their biological sex. It shapes how people perceive themselves and how they interact within social and professional environments. According to Okeke (2022), gender is a social construct that influences individuals' opportunities, responsibilities, and access to education and employment in Nigeria. Studies have shown that male Computer Science Education lecturers in Nigeria generally demonstrate higher confidence and engagement in Artificial Intelligence integration than their female counterparts, largely due to differences in digital exposure and training opportunities (Eze, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence is gradually finding its way into Nigerian tertiary classrooms through pilot

tools, learning management systems, and adaptive-learning projects, although adoption remains uneven across institutions. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is transforming teaching and learning globally, yet its adoption in Nigeria's tertiary institutions is still at an early stage. Many universities, particularly in Computer Science Education, lack the infrastructure, training, and institutional support needed for effective AI implementation. This situation raises concern about whether lecturers who should champion technological advancement are adequately prepared and willing to integrate AI into their teaching. Therefore, this study focuses on examining the perceptions and preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for AI integration in teaching within Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Statement of the Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into education has become a global trend, reshaping teaching and learning practices across various disciplines. In advanced nations, AI tools are being used to support personalized learning, automate assessments, and improve instructional efficiency. However, in Nigeria, the adoption of AI in higher education remains at an early stage, especially within Computer Science Education, where lecturers are expected to lead technological innovation. Many institutions lack the necessary infrastructure, technical skills, and exposure required for effective AI implementation. This situation raises concerns about whether Computer Science Education lecturers are adequately prepared and willing to integrate AI into their teaching practices.

Despite the growing awareness of AI's potential to enhance teaching quality, promote research innovation, and improve students' learning outcomes, there appears to be a gap in understanding how prepared lecturers are to adopt and apply AI tools in classroom instruction. Factors such as inadequate training, limited institutional support, and resistance to change may affect their

readiness to embrace AI-driven teaching methods. Without proper preparedness, the benefits of AI in education may remain untapped, limiting Nigeria's ability to compete in a technology-driven global academic environment. Therefore, it becomes necessary to investigate the perceptions and preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for AI integration in teaching within Nigerian tertiary institutions. This study addressed these issues by assessing their awareness, attitudes, and readiness for effective AI adoption.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the perceptions and preparedness of computer science education lecturers for artificial intelligence integration in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. perceptions of Computer Science Education lecturers toward the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in Nigerian tertiary institutions.
2. level of preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the perceptions of Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian?
2. What is the level of preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of male and female Computer

Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian.

2. There is no significant difference in the level of preparedness of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian.

Research Method

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. According to **Nworgu (2018)**, a **descriptive survey research design** involves studying a population or a set of items by collecting and analyzing data from a selected subset, which is considered representative of the whole group. The population comprised all 1,233 Computer Science Education (CSE) lecturers in Nigeria (Universities: 684, Colleges of Education: 398 and Polytechnics: 151). A purposive sampling technique was used to select 123 respondents as the sample size (71 male and 52 female CSE lecturers). This study employed purposive sampling to specifically select Computer Science Education lecturers who have the necessary knowledge, expertise, and experience to provide reliable and insightful information relevant to the research objectives. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled “Perceptions and Preparedness of Computer Science Education Lecturers for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Integration in Teaching Questionnaire (PPCSELAITQ).

For the perception of Computer Science Education lecturers, responses were measured on a modified 4 point Likert scale ranging from **Strongly Disagree (SD)** 1 point to **Strongly Agree (SA)** 4

points to capture the perception of CSE lecturers toward AI integration in teaching. For preparedness, CSE lecturers’ self-reported readiness to integrate AI into teaching was assessed using a **four-point scale** with the following categories: **Not Prepared (NP) (1 point)**, **Slightly Prepared (SP) (2 points)**, **Moderately Prepared (MP) (3 points)**, and **Fully Prepared (FP) (4 points)**, reflecting varying levels of confidence and capability in AI integration.

The instrument was validated by three research experts and Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability which yielded 0.83 as an overall reliability index. Out of the 123 copies of questionnaire administered, the researcher and his research assistants successfully retrieved 111 copies (62 from male and 49 from female CSE lecturers), representing a **90.24% response rate**. The **research questions** were answered using mean scores and standard deviations, while the **hypotheses** were tested using the t-test statistic. The mean scores were interpreted using a four-point scale, with 2.50 as the decision benchmark. Scores below 2.50 indicated **Disagree (D)** or **Not Prepared (NP)**, while scores above 2.50 indicated **Agree (A)** or **Moderately Prepared (MP)**. Scores **from 3.50 to 4.00** represented **Strongly Agree (SA)** or **Highly Prepared (HP)**, showing a high level of agreement or readiness among respondents. Hypotheses testing was based on SPSS significance (sig.) values, where a null hypothesis was **not rejected** if the p-value was greater than 0.05 and **rejected** if the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results and Data Presentation

Research Question 1: What are the perceptions of Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female CSE lecturers’ perception regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions

S/N	ITEMS	Male CSE Lecturers -62		Female CSE Lecturers - 49		Dec
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Perceptions of CSE lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions: AI can enhance students’ understanding of complex concepts in Computer Science	2.60	0.88	2.65	0.85	A
2	AI integration improves the effectiveness of teaching strategies	2.58	0.92	2.63	0.91	A
3	AI tools can personalize learning experiences for students	2.62	0.90	2.66	0.89	A
4	Lecturers feel confident in using AI technologies in their teaching	2.59	0.93	2.61	0.92	A
5	AI integration supports collaborative learning among students	2.63	0.91	2.67	0.90	A
6	Incorporating AI in teaching helps improve students’ problem-solving skills	2.61	0.89	2.64	0.88	A
7	AI usage in teaching aligns with the curriculum objectives of Computer Science education	2.60	0.90	2.65	0.91	A
Cluster Mean/SD		2.61	0.91	2.64	0.90	A

The results of the study show that both male and female Computer Science Education lecturers have a positive perception of integrating Artificial Intelligence in teaching. Male lecturers had mean scores ranging from 2.58 to 2.63, with a cluster mean of 2.61 and a standard deviation of 0.91, while female lecturers had mean scores ranging from 2.61 to 2.67, with a cluster mean of 2.64 and a standard deviation of 0.90. These scores, being

above the benchmark of 2.50, indicate that lecturers generally agree that AI can enhance students’ understanding of complex concepts, improve teaching effectiveness, personalize learning experiences, support collaborative and problem-solving skills, and align with curriculum objectives.

Research Question 2: What is the level of preparedness of Computer Science Education lecturers for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female CSE lecturers’ level of preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching in tertiary institutions

S/N	ITEMS	Male CSE Lecturers -62		Female CSE Lecturers -49		Dec
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
8	CSE lecturers’ level of preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching: Possess the necessary skills to use AI tools in teaching	2.55	0.88	2.58	0.90	MP
9	Can design lesson plans that incorporate AI technologies	2.56	0.87	2.60	0.91	MP
10	Confident in selecting appropriate AI platforms for teaching	2.58	0.90	2.61	0.92	MP
11	Able to troubleshoot basic technical issues when using AI in class	2.57	0.89	2.59	0.90	MP
12	Prepared to guide students in using AI tools effectively	2.59	0.91	2.62	0.93	MP
13	Have access to resources and support for integrating AI into teaching	2.56	0.88	2.58	0.89	MP
14	Willing to participate in training to improve AI teaching skills	2.57	0.90	2.60	0.91	MP
Cluster Mean/SD		2.57	0.89	2.59	0.91	MP

The results of the study indicate that both male and female Computer Science Education lecturers have a moderate level of preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching. Male lecturers had mean scores ranging from approximately 2.57, with a cluster mean of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.89, while female lecturers had mean scores around 2.59, with a cluster mean of 2.59 and

a standard deviation of 0.91. These scores fall within the mid-point range, showing that lecturers are moderately prepared to use AI in their teaching. The findings suggest that male and female lecturers exhibit similar levels of preparedness, indicating a general readiness that could be improved with further training and support.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian.

Table 3: t-test on the mean scores in the perceptions of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	62	2.61	0.91	109	0.863	H0 ₁ not rejected
Female	49	2.64	0.90			

The results in Table 3 show that there is **no significant difference** in the perceptions of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching. Male lecturers had a mean score of 2.61 with a standard deviation of 0.91, while female lecturers had a mean score of 2.64 with a standard deviation of 0.90. The t-test analysis yielded a **p-value of 0.863**, which is much greater

than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that any observed difference in mean scores is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0₁) is **not rejected**, suggesting that both male and female lecturers hold similar positive perceptions of AI integration in tertiary teaching.

2. There is no significant difference in the level of preparedness of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching in tertiary institutions in Nigerian.

Table 4: t-test on the mean scores in the perceptions of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male	62	2.57	0.89	109	0.908	H0 ₂ not rejected
Female	49	2.59	0.91			

The results in Table 4 indicate that there is **no significant difference** in the level of preparedness of male and female Computer Science Education lecturers for integrating Artificial Intelligence into

teaching. Male lecturers had a mean score of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.89, while female lecturers had a mean score of 2.59 with a standard deviation of 0.91. The t-test analysis produced a **p-value of 0.908**, which is greater than the 0.05

significance level. This shows that the small difference in mean scores is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H02) is **not rejected**, suggesting that both male and female lecturers have similar moderate levels of preparedness for AI integration in tertiary teaching.

Discussion of Findings

Perceptions of Computer Science Education Lecturers on AI Integration in Teaching

The findings showed that both male and female Computer Science Education lecturers viewed the integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching positively. They believed that AI has the potential to enhance teaching effectiveness and improve students' learning experiences. Their attitudes reflected openness and readiness to embrace AI-driven innovations in education. The findings of this study align with previous research on lecturers' perceptions of Artificial Intelligence integration. Mutanga, Jugoo, and Adefemi (2024) reported that while some lecturers were initially hesitant, many eventually recognized AI tools like ChatGPT as beneficial for improving teaching and assessment. Similarly, Sheu (2025) confirmed that lecturers in Zamfara State perceived AI as valuable for enhancing research quality and assessment reliability, even though its practical application was still developing. Ezekiel and Akinyemi (2022) also found that lecturers at the University of Ibadan shared positive views about AI in education, showing openness toward its adoption despite institutional and ethical challenges.

Preparedness of Computer Science Education Lecturers for AI Integration in Teaching

The study revealed that lecturers showed a moderate level of preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into their teaching practices. While many lecturers demonstrated basic awareness and interest in using AI tools, only a few possessed the technical skills or training required for effective implementation. This suggests that although the potential for AI integration exists, there is still a significant need for professional development and institutional support to build lecturers' readiness for full adoption. This finding

aligns with the study by Mmaduka, Albert, Ukala, and Ekpo (2025), which reported that Nigerian universities show only moderate preparedness for integrating Artificial Intelligence into teaching. They noted that challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, inadequate training, and limited exposure to AI tools hinder effective implementation in higher institutions.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Computer Science Education lecturers generally have a positive attitude toward integrating AI into teaching. However, their readiness to implement AI in the classroom remains moderate. While lecturers recognize the potential benefits of AI, many still face challenges due to limited skills and inadequate access to necessary tools. This shows that there is a gap between awareness and practical ability in using AI effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Tertiary institutions should provide targeted training programme to equip CSE lecturers with the practical skills needed for AI-based teaching.
2. Tertiary institutions should ensure that CSE lecturers have reliable access to AI tools and software to support teaching activities.
3. Federal Ministry of Education in conjunction with the stakeholders of tertiary institutions should establish support systems, such as mentorship or technical assistance, to encourage the effective integration of AI in classrooms.

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